

Experimental Demonstration of Optical Beamforming on a Dispersion-Engineered Heterogeneous Multicore Fiber

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Abstract: We report the experimental demonstration of tunable optical beamforming for phased-array antennas on a dispersion-engineered heterogeneous multicore fiber. We developed in-house both the fiber and the antenna and successfully demonstrated radio beam-steering at 26 GHz. © 2022 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Beyond high-capacity digital communications, multicore fibers (MCFs) [1] exhibit great potential in radio-over-fiber distribution and microwave signal processing scenarios. We have previously proposed the use of dispersion-engineered heterogeneous MCFs for compact fiber-distributed signal processing, i.e., the simultaneous processing and distribution of microwave signals [2]. This approach is based on the custom design of MCFs to act as tunable sampled true time delay lines (TTDLs) where every core provides at the output a different time-delayed version of the radiofrequency (RF) signal. TTDLs are actually the basis of many microwave signal processing functionalities, such as signal filtering, radio beam-steering for phased-array antennas (PAAs) or arbitrary signal generation.

Current optical beamforming networks use a MCF for mere distribution while the TTDL is implemented externally. In [3], optical beamforming was demonstrated on a 4-core homogeneous MCF, where the TTDL was realized via an optical chip, while in [4] they used a 7-core homogeneous MCF assisted with external optical delay lines. In this work, we report, for the first time to our knowledge, the experimental demonstration of optical beamforming for PAAs implemented on a 5-km heterogeneous MCF. We successfully demonstrated radio beam-steering in an in-house fabricated 8-element PAA at the RF frequency of 26 GHz exploiting dispersion diversity in a customized fully heterogeneous 7-core fiber.

2. Multicore fiber true time delay line

We have developed a 7-core heterogeneous MCF that operates as a sampled true time delay line, [5]. Each fiber core was designed with particular radial dimensions and core material composition to provide a particular group-delay dependence with the optical wavelength. The fiber was fabricated by YOFC company. It is 5-km long and consists of 7 trench-assisted step-index cores placed in a hexagonal disposition inside a 150- μm fiber cladding diameter, with a 40- μm core pitch. Fig. 1 (a) shows a photograph of the fabricated MCF. The measured worst-case crosstalk for the 5-km MCF link is below -30 dB while the average insertion losses are 5.8 dB.

Fig. 1 (b) depicts the measured spectral differential group delays between core 7 and the rest. We see that while cores 3 up to 7 provide a constant basic differential group delay between adjacent samples, cores 1 and 2 -which are the smallest cores and thus most sensitive to fabrication errors- do not satisfy plenty the incremental chromatic dispersion condition. Then, up to 5-sample TTDL operation can be implemented in the space-diversity domain by using cores 3 up to 7, while all 7 cores are applicable to operate in the wavelength diversity domain or to implement any other application that does not require space-diversity signal processing with a constant basic differential delay.

Fig. 1. a) Photograph of the cross-section of the fabricated 7-core heterogeneous MCF. (b) Measured differential group delay versus the optical wavelength for the MCF cores with respect to core 7. (c) Photograph of the 8-element phased-array antenna. (d)

Measured beam-pattern of 1 antenna element. (e) Photograph of the experimental optical beamforming setup mounted inside the anechoic chamber.

3. Experiment

To begin with, we designed and fabricated an 8-element microstrip PAA with an element spacing of $d = 5.8$ mm ($0.5\lambda_0$ at 26 GHz). Fig. 1 (c) shows a picture of the fabricated antenna. Each path was properly designed to ensure that the signals that feed each antenna element experience identical time delays. Fig. 1 (d) illustrates the measured embedded radiation pattern of a representative antenna element. The far-field radiation pattern was measured by introducing the antenna inside an anechoic chamber, as Fig. 1 (e) shows. At $f_0 = 26$ GHz the differential delay needed to produce a phase shift of $[-\pi, \pi]$ between antenna elements is $[-1/(2f_0), 1/(2f_0)]$. This condition narrows down the delay tunability range to 38.4 ps approximately. To tune the beam-pointing angle of the antenna continuously, we choose the wavelength range that goes from 1541.54 to 1549.24 nm. As cores 1 and 2 don't comply with the required differential delays, we implement a 1x5 beamformer network using cores 3 to 7 (C3-C7).

Finally, we experimentally demonstrate optical beamforming by setting the antenna in the anechoic chamber and measuring the radiation pattern by means of a receiver horn antenna. Fig 2 (a) represents the setup used to measure the radiation pattern of the PAA. First, the optical signal coming from a tunable laser is modulated using a dual-drive external modulator (EOM) with the RF signal generated by a microwave signal generator. This signal is then amplified using an erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) and launched into the corresponding cores with uniform power distribution. The signal from each core is detected and amplified using independent photodiodes and RF amplifiers. The PAA and the required optical and electrical devices are placed inside the anechoic chamber and onto an antenna positioner. The transmitter and receiver antennas are separated 3 meters. We then measured the radiation pattern at different optical wavelengths ranging from 1542.50 to 1548.28 nm in steps of 0.96 nm. This translates into time delays provided by the TTDL from 62.5 to 91.36 ps in steps of 4.81 ps approximately. Fig 2 (b) depicts the measured radiation pattern for 7 different optical wavelengths. The resulting beam pointing angle varies approximately from -40° up to 43° . Minor discrepancies on the differential delay between cores affect the radiation pattern, causing main lobe broadening at angles farther from broadside direction and shifting the beam-pointing angle slightly. The radiation pattern of the antenna elements also takes part here as it has substantial power variations, and these affect the main lobe shape. As Fig. 1 (d) shows, for absolute angles greater than 45° , the received power drops considerably and this limits the maximum beamforming angles we can achieve.

Fig. 2. a) Experimental setup for optical beamforming in the fabricated phased array antenna. b) Measured radiation pattern of the phased array antenna for an RF frequency of 26 GHz and different optical wavelengths.

4. Conclusions

We experimentally demonstrated here continuously tunable optical beamforming for phase array antennas built upon a dispersion-engineered heterogeneous multicore fiber. The 5-km multicore fiber link comprises 7 different trench-assisted cores, where the refractive index profile of each core is individually addressed to fulfil the requirements for sampled tunable TTDL operation while providing low intercore crosstalk. The 5-element radiation pattern of a phased-array antenna was measured in an anechoic chamber for an RF frequency of 26 GHz. We successfully demonstrate how the beam can be steered at different angles just by varying the optical wavelength of the laser.

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